

FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES OF ART THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH NON-ORGANIC PSYCHOSIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18241989>

ABSTRACT: Relevance. Patients with inorganic psychosis experience significant limitations in social and professional functioning, along with impairments in cognitive and psychological skills. This condition requires the implementation of innovative methods for effective rehabilitation and social reintegration. Objective. To develop the principles and methodology of Art Therapy for patients with inorganic psychosis and to determine its effectiveness in the treatment process based on an analysis of clinical-psychopathological and pathopsychological characteristics. Materials and Methods. The study included 150 patients aged 18–45 years with inorganic psychotic disorders (F20–F29). The qualification of mental disorders was determined according to ICD-10 criteria. The PANSS scale was used for formalized statistical assessment of clinico-psychopathological dynamics. Cognitive functions were assessed based on Luria’s approaches. Personal characteristics were evaluated using the Kellermann-Plutchik Lifestyle Index, and changes in behavioral patterns were analyzed using the “copy behavior” methodology in stressful situations. Social activity indicators were studied using the psychiatric scale for limiting life activity. Results. Most patients lived with parents or relatives. During the acute psychotic episode, hallucinatory-paranoid, paranoid, and depressive-paranoid syndromes predominated. The Art Therapy methodology focuses on correcting cognitive processes, developing constructive intrapsychic coping strategies, processing emotional information via non-verbal channels, and strengthening adaptive mechanisms of psychological protection. Conclusions. The study demonstrated that Art Therapy is an effective tool for the psychorehabilitation of patients with inorganic psychosis, contributing to the development of cognitive and social skills and optimizing the therapeutic process.

Keywords: inorganic psychosis, Art Therapy, psychorehabilitation, cognitive functions, psychopathology.

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ АРТ-ТЕРАПИИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С НЕОРГАНИЧЕСКИМ ПСИХОЗОМ

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Аннотация: Актуальность. Пациенты с неорганическим психозом сталкиваются с существенными ограничениями в социальной и профессиональной деятельности, а также наблюдаются нарушения когнитивных и психологических функций. Данное состояние требует внедрения инновационных методов для эффективной реабилитации и социальной интеграции

пациентов. Цель. Разработка принципов и методологии арт-терапии для пациентов с неорганическим психозом, а также определение ее эффективности в процессе лечения на основе анализа клинико-психопатологических и патопсихологических особенностей. Материалы и методы. В исследование были включены 150 пациентов с неорганическими психотическими расстройствами (F20–F29) в возрасте 18–45 лет. Квалификация психических расстройств определялась на основе критериев ICD-10. Для формализованной оценки динамики клинико-психопатологических проявлений использовалась шкала PANSS. Когнитивные функции оценивались по подходам Лурии. Для изучения личностных характеристик использовался опросник «Индекс образа жизни» Келлермана–Плутчика, для анализа поведенческих изменений применялась методика «копирующего поведения» в стрессовых ситуациях. Социальная активность изучалась с помощью психиатрической шкалы ограничения жизнедеятельности. Результаты. Большинство пациентов жили с родителями или родственниками. В период острого психотического эпизода преобладали галлюцинаторно-параноидальный, параноидальный и депрессивно-параноидальный синдромы. Методология арт-терапии направлена на коррекцию когнитивных процессов, развитие конструктивных внутриспсихических стратегий, переработку эмоциональной информации через невербальные каналы и укрепление адаптивных механизмов психологической защиты. Выводы. Исследование показало, что арт-терапия является эффективным средством психореабилитации пациентов с неорганическим психозом, способствует формированию когнитивных и социальных навыков и оптимизирует терапевтический процесс.

Ключевые слова: неорганический психоз, арт-терапия, психореабилитация, когнитивные функции, психопатология.

NORGANIK PSIXOZ BILAN KASALLANGAN BEMORLARDA ART TERAPIYASINING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Dolzarblik. Norganik psixozga chalingan bemorlar ijtimoiy va kasbiy faoliyatda sezilarli cheklovlarga duch keladi, shuningdek, kognitiv va psixologik ko‘nikmalarda buzilishlar kuzatiladi. Ushbu holat bemorlarni samarali reabilitatsiya qilish va ijtimoiy integratsiyasini ta‘minlash uchun innovatsion metodlarni joriy etishni talab qiladi. Maqsad. Norganik psixoz bilan kasallangan bemorlar uchun san‘at terapiyasi (Art therapy) tamoyillari va metodologiyasini ishlab chiqish, klinik-psixopatologik va patopsixologik xususiyatlarni tahlil qilish asosida davolash jarayonida samarali qo‘llanishini aniqlash. Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqotga 18–45 yoshdagi 150 nafar F20–29 guruhidagi norganik psixotik kasalliklarga chalingan bemorlar kiritilgan. Diagnostika ICD-10 mezonlariga asoslangan. PANSS skala va Luria yondashuvlari orqali kognitiv faoliyat baholangan. Bemorlarning shaxsiy xususiyatlari, xulq-atvori va ijtimoiy faoliyati psixodiagnostik metodlar va ijtimoiy faoliyatni baholash vositalari yordamida tahlil qilingan. Natijalar. Bemorlarning ko‘pchiligi yolg‘iz yashagan yoki ota-ona/qarindoshlar bilan yashagan. Akut psixotik epizodlarda hallusinator-paranoid, paranoid va depressiv-paranoid sindromlar ko‘p kuzatilgan. San‘at terapiyasi metodologiyasi kognitiv jarayonlarni

korreksiya qilish, biopsixososial yondashuv, konstruktiv intrapsixik strategiyalarni rivojlantirish, noverbal kanallar orqali emotsiyalarni qayta ishlash va adaptiv psixologik himoya mexanizmlarini mustahkamlashga asoslangan. Xulosa. Tadqiqot san'at terapiyasining norganik psixozga chalingan bemorlar reabilitatsiyasida samarali vosita ekanligini ko'rsatdi, bu bemorlarning kognitiv va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga yordam beradi hamda terapevtik jarayonni optimallashtiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: norganik psixoz, san'at terapiyasi, Art therapy, psixoreabilitatsiya, kognitiv funktsiyalar, psixopatologiya.

Introduction. According to the World Health Organization, acute psychosis is considered the third leading condition causing disability worldwide, ranking just after major chronic illnesses in terms of social and occupational impairment. Individuals affected by severe psychotic disorders experience a reduction in average life expectancy of approximately ten years due to the combined effects of the disease itself and associated comorbidities [1-3]. Typically, the onset of psychosis occurs at a young age, often during late adolescence or early adulthood, which profoundly disrupts key domains of life, including social relationships, professional engagement, and family functioning. Moreover, the presence of acute psychotic episodes has secondary effects on the social functioning of healthy family members, who often experience increased stress, caregiver burden, and limitations in their social roles [4-7].

Contemporary research demonstrates that acute psychotic episodes frequently recur, with 57-67% of patients experiencing at least one relapse within the first year following initial onset, and between 69-95,5% experiencing relapse within five years [8-11]. Each subsequent episode not only imposes significant economic and social costs but also exacerbates cognitive deficits, leading to progressive deterioration of executive, memory, and attention functions. This progressive decline often results in premature disability, underscoring the need for timely and comprehensive intervention.

Despite the sometimes atypical or "uncharacteristic" clinical presentation of early psychotic episodes (EPEs), these patients clearly meet criteria for early rehabilitation interventions. Psychotherapy plays a central role in such interventions, facilitating early social reintegration and improving long-term outcomes [12-15]. Evidence from both domestic and international research indicates that the most effective psychosocial interventions include psychoeducation for patients and their relatives, structured family therapy, and targeted training aimed at improving social skills and cognitive functioning. Longitudinal clinical experience further confirms that early and sustained engagement in these interventions reduces relapse risk, enhances functional recovery, and mitigates the severity of future episodes [16].

In recent years, international studies have increasingly recognized the potential of Art Therapy as a complementary intervention for patients with acute psychosis. Art Therapy provides a structured, non-verbal means of expression, enabling patients to externalize emotional distress, explore internal conflicts, and engage in creative problem-solving within a therapeutic context [17-20]. By integrating cognitive, emotional, and social domains, Art Therapy has been shown to promote self-awareness, improve affect regulation, and strengthen coping mechanisms, making it a valuable component of comprehensive psychosocial rehabilitation.

The purpose of the study. The study aims to develop and systematize the fundamental principles of Art Therapy specifically tailored for patients diagnosed with inorganic psychotic disorders (F20-F29). This approach is grounded in a thorough and comprehensive analysis of the clinical, psychopathological, and pathopsychological characteristics of this patient population throughout the course of treatment. By

examining the dynamic patterns of symptom expression, cognitive and emotional functioning, and behavioral responses, the research seeks to establish evidence-based guidelines for the effective implementation of Art Therapy as an integral component of psychosocial rehabilitation.

Materials and methods. The study sample consisted of 150 patients diagnosed with inorganic psychotic disorders (F20-F29), aged between 18 and 45 years. The classification and confirmation of the mental disorders were conducted in accordance with the clinical and diagnostic criteria outlined in the ICD-10. To quantitatively evaluate the dynamics of clinical-psychopathological symptoms, a standardized scale of positive and negative symptoms (PANSS) was utilized. Cognitive impairments were assessed following A.R. Luria's methodologies, which provide a structured approach to analyzing higher mental functions and their disorders.

To examine personal characteristics and the functioning of psychological defense mechanisms, the “Lifestyle Index” questionnaire by Kellermann–Plutchik was applied. Changes in behavioral patterns, particularly the frequency and severity of coping strategies employed under stress, were evaluated using a structured “copy behavior” methodology. Furthermore, the social functioning and performance in social roles of patients were assessed using the relevant sections of psychiatric disability scales, allowing for a formalized measurement of limitations in life activities.

The median age of participants was $27,8 \pm 4,2$ years. The gender distribution indicated a predominance of males, who comprised $61,3 \pm 4,8\%$ of the sample, compared to females, who accounted for $38,6 \pm 4,8\%$, reflecting a ratio of approximately 2:1. This demographic information provides essential context for understanding the sample characteristics and potential gender-related differences in clinical presentation and treatment response.

Methodologically, the study employed a combination of structural-functional and structural-level analyses, clinical-psychopathological, clinical-anamnestic, clinical-catamnestic, psychodiagnostic, sociodemographic, and statistical approaches to ensure a comprehensive assessment of the clinical and social features of patients.

The methodological and organizational principles of Art therapy for patients with inorganic psychosis were formulated as interventions aimed at correcting fundamental cognitive processes. These principles are grounded in international standards, the biopsychosocial model of mental disorder development, and the medical-psychological concept of creativity. The therapy focuses on intrapsychic organization of constructive coping strategies to manage polymodal stressors and mitigate distressing factors. This is achieved through non-verbal channels of perception, facilitating adaptive emotional processing of environmental information, and promoting the restoration of psychological protective mechanisms.

Results and their discussion. During the initial phase of the study, it was found that the majority of patients were unmarried, comprising $65,3 \pm 4,8\%$ of the sample. Most participants lived with their parents or other relatives ($70,0 \pm 4,6\%$), indicating a high degree of familial dependency and social support. Educational levels were distributed as follows: average general education – $49,3 \pm 5,0\%$; specialized secondary education – $30,7 \pm 4,6\%$; higher education – $12,7 \pm 3,3\%$; and incomplete higher education – $7,3 \pm 2,6\%$. Regarding employment, $20,6 \pm 4,0\%$ of participants were engaged in physical work with reduced qualifications, $9,3 \pm 2,9\%$ in physical work without reduced qualifications, $7,3 \pm 2,6\%$ in unskilled physical labor, and $3,3 \pm 1,8\%$ were engaged in mental work with reduced qualifications.

In addition to deficits in skills, a substantial proportion of patients demonstrated reduced labor activity: $59,3 \pm 5,0\%$ were unemployed, $24,6 \pm 4,3\%$ maintained continuous employment, while $16,0 \pm 3,7\%$ were employed intermittently. The acute phase of illness lasted on average $25,9 \pm 4,8$ months. During this phase, the clinical presentation included both psychopathological and characterological changes. Psychopathological symptoms were polymorphic: emotional disturbances were observed in $69,3 \pm 4,6\%$ of cases, thought disorders in $67,3 \pm 4,7\%$, effector-volitional impairments in $50,7 \pm 5,0\%$, perceptual disorders in $37,3 \pm 4,8\%$, and somatic concerns in $36,0 \pm 4,8\%$. Characterological changes included signs of passivity and subordination ($67,3 \pm 4,7\%$), dependent behavior ($22,7 \pm 4,2\%$), social isolation ($28,6 \pm 4,5\%$), apathy ($14,3 \pm 4,5\%$), and mild, inefficient hyperactivity ($5,1 \pm 2,2\%$).

The syndromic structure of actual psychotic episodes revealed predominance of hallucinatory-paranoid syndrome ($40,7 \pm 4,9\%$), followed by paranoid syndrome ($28,7 \pm 4,5\%$), depressive-paranoid syndrome ($27,3 \pm 4,5\%$), and a smaller proportion with manic-paranoid syndrome ($3,3 \pm 1,8\%$).

Universal methodological principles of Art therapy encompass consistency, complexity, individualization (differentiated approach), continuity and permanence, staging, timeliness of intervention, and dynamic monitoring.

The principle of consistency is grounded in the integrative nature of art and creativity, forming the foundation for all types of psychotherapy and psychotherapeutic interactions embedded in traditional therapeutic systems. Art therapy techniques exert therapeutic effects across biological, psychological, social, and spiritual domains.

The principle of complexity refers to the simultaneous application of multiple creative modalities addressing evolutionarily distinct behavioral patterns. These include a broad spectrum of olfactory (contact-based) and audiovisual (remote) interactions, expressive pictorial techniques, body pantomime and dance-plastic exercises, audio-musical (vocal and instrumental) methods, visual presentations utilizing color, shape, texture, and imagery, as well as theatrical techniques to simulate dramatic scenarios that facilitate the acquisition of adaptive behaviors applicable to daily life.

The differential (individual) approach allows for the personalization and optimization of Art-therapeutic interventions by taking into account premorbid personality traits, the profile of positive and negative psychopathological symptoms, cognitive function levels, and current psychological resources of the patient. This approach incorporates dynamic selection of intervention topics according to the patient's mood (guided by Altshuller's isoprinciple) and adjustment of psycho-emotional intensity.

Art therapy is designed as a long-term intervention, consisting of two consecutive blocks: the main (intensive) block conducted during inpatient treatment and the supportive block conducted in an outpatient or community setting. The main block spans 2 months and includes three stages: (1) psychodiagnostics and organizational training, (2) symptomatic correction, and (3) personal reconstruction. The supportive block extends over 24 months, focusing on maintaining positive change. The initial psychodiagnostic and organizational stage lasts two weeks, with Art therapy sessions conducted twice weekly during the first 11–14 days of hospitalization. The symptomatic correction phase also lasts two weeks, with four sessions per week (8 lessons). The personal reconstruction stage lasts four weeks, with session frequency gradually reduced from three times per week (6 lessons) to twice per week (4 lessons). During the support phase, sessions occur once weekly for two years (96 lessons).

The total number of Art-therapeutic sessions is 117, with each session lasting between 45–90 minutes depending on the stage. Group therapy is sufficient to facilitate resource mobilization, self-

regulation, and the development of effective communication skills. The main block is conducted in closed groups, while the supportive block uses partially open groups under the guidance of a psychiatrist/psychotherapist and a medical psychologist.

Session structure and methodology utilize thematic and analytical approaches. The content of each session is adapted to the initial capabilities of participants, the dynamics of the group process, and progress in skill acquisition. This ensures gradual increases in load across various domains of personal activity, encourages self-expression, develops life skills, and enhances the therapeutic potential of the group. Complexity is augmented by introducing multiple emotional modalities, including musical, auditory, and kinesthetic Art-plastic exercises integrated with visual tasks. The intensity of sessions increases through activation of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic emotions, verbal expression of experienced feelings, and growing passive and active engagement in group interactions, including pair and small group exercises, as well as reflective analysis.

Each session consists of three core stages: (1) introduction (attitude setting), (2) main creative work (creative load), and (3) discussion (completion). Sessions include both repetitive and novel exercises. At the start, participants share their current mood and impressions, while at the end, a “collective handshake” ritual fosters a supportive group climate. Sessions are conducted in a fully equipped Art therapy center with all necessary materials, at pre-scheduled times.

Conclusions. The principle of staging ensures coordinated management of therapy as a unified temporal plan, integrating traditional treatment and Art-therapeutic training. The principle of timeliness activates Art therapy in the early post-acute phase to create a psychotherapeutic “window,” respecting the chronological and structural sequence of intensive, core, and supportive program components. The principle of dynamic monitoring provides continuous assessment of patient and group status, allowing real-time adjustments to optimize therapeutic effects and control interactions.

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